

Figure E1. STROBE diagram

Predictive margins	HR	Std. Err.	z	95%CI
No CPFE + No Tobacco Smoking	0.71	0.25	2.82	0.22 - 1.21
No CPFE + Tobacco Smoking	1.11	0.40	2.78	0.33 - 1.89
CPFE + No Tobacco Smoking	0.90	0.43	2.10	0.06 - 1.74
CPFE + Tobacco Smoking	1.05	0.39	2.70	0.29 - 1.81

Definition of abbreviations: CI = confidence interval; HR=hazard ratio; ILD=interstitial lung disease *Computed using Cox proportional hazard models.

Models assessing tobacco smoking and CPFE with adjustment for age, sex, forced vital capacity at ILD diagnosis, diffusing capacity of the lungs for carbon monoxide at ILD diagnosis, ILD subtype, and antifibrotic therapy.

Figure E2. Cox Mortality Hazard Model Assessing the Interaction between Tobacco Smoking and Combined Pulmonary Fibrosis and Emphysema (CPFE)

Table E1. Baseline characteristics of study participants in the non-tertiary cohort stratified by tobacco smoking

Characteristic	Tobacco Smoker n=188	Tobacco Non-Smoker n=289	Total Cohort n=477
Age in years, mean (SD)	72 (11)	72 (12)	72 (12)
Male gender, n (%)	91 (48%)	127 (44%)	218 (46%)
Race/ethnicity			
White race, n (%)	166 (89%)	220 (82%)	386 (85%)
Black race, n (%)	16 (9%)	9 (3%)	25 (5%)
Hispanic ethnicity, n (%)	1 (1%)	8 (3%)	9 (2%)
Asian/other race, n (%)	4 (2%)	31 (12%)	35 (8%)
BMI, mean (SD)	29 (6)	28 (6)	28 (6)
Clinical features			
Crackles, n (%)	48 (79%)	127 (65%)	175 (68%)
Digital clubbing, n (%)	15 (8%)	22 (8%)	37 (8%)
ILD subtype			
IPF, n (%)	96 (51%)	201 (70%)	297 (63%)
CTD-ILD, n (%)	8 (4%)	5 (2%)	13 (3%)
Fibrotic HP, n (%)	4 (2%)	5 (2%)	9 (2%)
Unclassifiable/Other ILD, n (%)	80 (43%)	78 (27%)	158 (33%)
Co-morbidities			
GERD, n (%)	83 (44%)	103 (36%)	186 (39%)
Coronary artery disease, n (%)	58 (31%)	65 (22%)	123 (26%)
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	36 (19%)	50 (17%)	86 (18%)
Hypothyroidism, n (%)	27 (17%)	26 (21%)	53 (19%)
HRCT features			
Emphysema, n (%)	35 (22%)	9 (7%)	44 (16%)
Radiologic fibrosis, n (%)	141 (75%)	195 (67%)	336 (70%)
Radiologic honeycombing, n (%)	66 (35%)	89 (31%)	155 (33%)
CPFE, n (%)	28 (15%)	6 (2%)	34 (7%)
Antifibrotic therapy, n (%)	36 (19%)	24 (8%)	60 (13%)
Immunosuppressive therapy, n (%)	133 (71%)	188 (65%)	321 (67%)
Lung function			
FVC %, mean (SD)	73 (20)	71 (19)	72 (19)
DLCO %, mean (SD)	47 (21)	47 (19)	47 (19)
Oxygen			
Use of supplemental O ₂ , n (%)	58 (31%)	79 (27%)	137 (29%)
O ₂ flow rate in lpm, mean (SD)	2 (1)	3 (3)	3 (2)

CT = computed tomography; DLCO = diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide; FVC = forced vital capacity; ILD = interstitial lung disease; IPF=Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, CPFE = combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema; CTD-ILD = Connective tissue disease-ILD, HP = Fibrotic Hypersensitivity pneumonitis, IPAF=interstitial pneumonia with autoimmune features. SD = standard deviation. LPM=liters per minute. Total sample size, N = 477. Categorical variables presented as n (%); continuous variables presented as mean (SD). Exception for participants: body mass index, n = 1157; crackles, n = 1159; clubbing, n = 1159; FVC, n = 1,163; DLCO, n = 1,037; immunosuppressive therapy, n = 1,163; antifibrotic therapy, n = 1,163; emphysema, n = 1163; antinuclear antibody, n = 1084; hypothyroidism, n = 1158; diabetes, n = 1158; coronary artery disease, n = 1158; gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), n = 1158; idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, n = 388; interstitial pneumonia with autoimmune features, n = 118; connective tissue disease-associated ILD, n = 266; chronic hypersensitivity pneumonitis, n = 159; unclassifiable/ other ILD, n = 232.

Table E2. Baseline characteristics of study participants in the tertiary IPF cohort stratified by tobacco smoking

Characteristic	Tobacco Smoker n= 257	Tobacco Non-Smoker n= 131	Total Cohort n= 388
Age in years, mean (SD)	69 (8)	68 (10)	69 (8)
Male gender, n (%)	207 (81)	73 (56)	280 (72)
Race/ethnicity			
White race, n (%)	222 (66)	113 (33)	335 (86)
Black race, n (%)	16 (76)	5 (24)	21 (5)
Hispanic ethnicity, n (%)	12 (75)	4 (25)	16 (4)
Asian/other race, n (%)	7 (44)	9 (56)	16 (4)
BMI, mean (SD)	30 (5)	30 (6)	30 (5)
Clinical features			
Crackles, n (%)	244 (95)	116 (89)	360 (93)
Digital clubbing, n (%)	46 (18)	20 (15)	66 (17)
Co-morbidities			
GERD, n (%)	129 (50)	77 (59)	206 (53)
Coronary artery disease, n (%)	65 (25)	27 (21)	92 (24)
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	57 (22)	24 (18)	81 (21)
Hypothyroidism, n (%)	29 (11)	24 (18)	53 (14)
HRCT features			
Emphysema, n (%)	80 (33)	13 (11)	93 (25)
Radiologic fibrosis*, n (%)	227 (90)	103 (81)	330 (87)
Radiologic honeycombing, n (%)	130 (52)	60 (47)	190 (50)
CPFE, n (%)	71 (28)	11 (8)	82 (21)
Antifibrotic therapy, n (%)	62 (24)	41 (31)	103 (27)
Lung function			
FVC %, mean (SD)	69 (18)	68 (20)	69 (19)
DLCO %, mean (SD)	51 (19)	58 (21)	53 (20)
Oxygen			
Use of supplemental O ₂ , n (%)	68 (27)	19 (15)	87 (22)
O ₂ flow rate in lpm, mean (SD)	4 (2)	3 (1)	4 (2)

CT = computed tomography; DLCO = diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide; FVC = forced vital capacity; ILD = interstitial lung disease; IPF=Idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis, CPFE = combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema; SD = standard deviation. LPM=liters per minute. Total sample size, N = 388. Categorical variables presented as n (%); continuous variables presented as mean (SD). *Radiologic fibrosis as determined on official CT documentation for presence of traction bronchiectasis or radiologic honeycombing. Exception for participants: body mass index, n = 385; emphysema, n = 366; radiologic fibrosis, n= 378; radiologic honeycombing, n= 378; DLCO, n = 347; supplemental O₂, n= 387

Table E3. Baseline characteristics of study participants in the tertiary CTD-related ILD cohort stratified by tobacco smoking

Characteristic	Tobacco Smoker n= 113	Tobacco Non-Smoker n= 153	Total Cohort n= 266
Age in years, mean (SD)	59 (10)	53 (14)	266 (13)
Male gender, n (%)	38 (34)	36 (24)	74 (28)
Race/ethnicity			
White race, n (%)	60 (45)	73 (55)	133 (50)
Black race, n (%)	33 (41)	48 (59)	81 (30)
Hispanic ethnicity, n (%)	9 (39)	14 (61)	23 (9)
Asian/other race, n (%)	11 (38)	18 (62)	29 (11)
BMI, mean (SD)	30 (7)	30 (6)	30 (7)
Clinical features			
Crackles, n (%)	86 (76)	124 (81)	210 (79)
Digital clubbing, n (%)	8 (7)	12 (8)	20 (8)
Co-morbidities			
GERD, n (%)	54 (48)	75 (49)	129 (49)
Coronary artery disease, n (%)	21 (19)	7 (5)	28 (11)
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	18 (16)	24 (16)	42 (16)
Hypothyroidism, n (%)	14 (12)	29 (19)	43 (16)
HRCT features			
Emphysema, n (%)	34 (33)	12 (9)	46 (19)
Radiologic fibrosis, n (%)	80 (71)	98 (66)	178 (68)
Radiologic honeycombing, n (%)	49 (43)	58 (39)	107 (41)
CPFE, n (%)	25 (22)	9 (6)	34 (13)
Antifibrotic therapy, n (%)	3 (3)	10 (7)	13 (5)
Lung function			
FVC %, mean (SD)	68 (20)	62 (19)	65 (20)
DLCO %, mean (SD)	57 (21)	61 (24)	59 (23)
Oxygen			
Use of supplemental O ₂ , n (%)	23 (21)	19 (13)	42 (16)
O ₂ flow rate in lpm, mean (SD)	4 (2)	3 (1)	3 (2)

CT = computed tomography; DLCO = diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide; FVC = forced vital capacity; ILD = interstitial lung disease; CPFE = combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema; CTD = connective tissue disease; SD = standard deviation. LPM=liters per minute. Total sample size, N = 266. Categorical variables presented as n (%); continuous variables presented as mean (SD). Exception for participants: gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), n= 265; hypothyroidism, n = 265; emphysema, n = 237; radiologic fibrosis, n= 262; radiologic honeycombing, n= 262; DLCO, n= 230; supplemental O₂, n= 259

Table E4. Baseline characteristics of study participants in the tertiary HP cohort stratified by tobacco smoking

Characteristic	Tobacco Smoker n= 91	Tobacco Non-Smoker n= 68	Total Cohort n= 159
Age in years, mean (SD)	64 (9)	63 (12)	159 (10)
Male gender, n (%)	44 (48)	21 (31)	65 (41)
Race/ethnicity			
White race, n (%)	83 (61)	52 (39)	135 (85)
Black race, n (%)	5 (38)	8 (62)	13 (8)
Hispanic ethnicity, n (%)	2 (29)	5 (71)	7 (4)
Asian/other race, n (%)	1 (25)	3 (75)	4 (3)
BMI, mean (SD)	32 (8)	31 (7)	32 (8)
Clinical features			
Crackles, n (%)	80 (88)	57 (84)	137 (86)
Digital clubbing, n (%)	18 (20)	12 (18)	30 (19)
Co-morbidities			
GERD, n (%)	59 (65)	28 (41)	87 (55)
Coronary artery disease, n (%)	16 (18)	10 (15)	26 (16)
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	20 (22)	15 (22)	25 (22)
Hypothyroidism, n (%)	18 (20)	15 (22)	33 (21)
HRCT features			
Emphysema, n (%)	25 (28)	12 (19)	37 (24)
Radiologic fibrosis, n (%)	69 (78)	50 (77)	119 (77)
Radiologic honeycombing, n (%)	36 (40)	18 (28)	54 (35)
CPFE, n (%)	20 (22)	9 (13)	29 (18)
Antifibrotic therapy, n (%)	5 (5)	5 (7)	10 (6)
Lung function			
FVC %, mean (SD)	68 (16)	62 (20)	65 (18)
DLCO %, mean (SD)	58 (20)	60 (26)	59 (22)
Oxygen			
Use of supplemental O ₂ , n (%)	30 (33)	18 (26)	48 (30)
O ₂ flow rate in lpm, mean (SD)	4 (2)	4 (1)	4 (1)

CT = computed tomography; DLCO = diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide; FVC = forced vital capacity; ILD = interstitial lung disease; HP = hypersensitivity pneumonitis; CPFE = combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema; SD = standard deviation. LPM=liters per minute. Total sample size, N = 159. Categorical variables presented as n (%); continuous variables presented as mean (SD). Exception for participants: body mass index, n = 158; emphysema, n = 154; radiologic fibrosis, n = 154; radiologic honeycombing, n = 154; DLCO, n = 144; supplemental O₂, n = 158

Table E5. Baseline characteristics of study participants in the tertiary unclassifiable/other ILD cohort* stratified by tobacco smoking

Characteristic	Tobacco Smoker n= 190	Tobacco Non-Smoker n= 160	Total Cohort n= 350
Age in years, mean (SD)	62 (12)	57 (13)	60 (13)
Male gender, n (%)	96 (51)	59 (37)	155 (44)
Race/ethnicity			
White race, n (%)	137 (59)	95 (41)	232(66)
Black race, n (%)	41 (46)	49 (54)	90 (26)
Hispanic ethnicity, n (%)	6 (50)	6 (50)	12 (3)
Asian/other race, n (%)	6 (38)	10 (63)	16 (5)
BMI, mean (SD)	31 (6)	30 (7)	31 (7)
Clinical features			
Crackles, n (%)	142 (75)	93 (59)	235 (68)
Digital clubbing, n (%)	17 (9)	11 (7)	28 (8)
Co-morbidities			
GERD, n (%)	84 (45)	63 (40)	147 (42)
Coronary artery disease, n (%)	41 (22)	10 (6)	51 (15)
Diabetes mellitus, n (%)	41 (22)	18 (11)	59 (17)
Hypothyroidism, n (%)	30 (16)	12 (8)	42 (12)
HRCT features			
Emphysema, n (%)	37 (36)	7 (10)	44 (25)
Radiologic fibrosis, n (%)	99 (55)	71 (47)	170 (51)
Radiologic honeycombing, n (%)	72 (40)	42 (28)	114 (34)
CPFE, n (%)	17 (9)	4 (3)	21 (6)
Antifibrotic therapy, n (%)	22 (12)	12 (8)	34 (10)
Immunosuppressive therapy, n (%)			
Lung function			
FVC %, mean (SD)	68 (20)	66 (20)	67 (20)
DLCO %, mean (SD)	56 (24)	60 (26)	58 (25)
Oxygen			
Use of supplemental O ₂ , n (%)	44 (23)	28 (18)	72 (21)
O ₂ flow rate in lpm, mean (SD)	4 (2)	4 (2)	4 (2)

CT = computed tomography; DLCO = diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide; FVC = forced vital capacity; ILD = interstitial lung disease; CPFE = combined pulmonary fibrosis and emphysema; SD = standard deviation. LPM=liters per minute. Total sample size, N = 350. Categorical variables presented as n (%); continuous variables presented as mean (SD). Exception for participants: body mass index, n = 348; crackles, n = 346; clubbing, n = 346; gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD), n = 346; coronary artery disease, n = 345; diabetes, n = 345; hypothyroidism, n = 346; emphysema, n = 174; radiologic fibrosis, n = 331; radiologic honeycombing, n = 331; DLCO, n = 316; supplemental O₂, n = 344; *unclassifiable, interstitial pneumonia with autoimmune features, and other ILD

Table E6. Baseline characteristics of patients in the tertiary center cohort stratified by radiologic emphysema

Characteristic	Emphysema n= 220	Non-emphysema n= 711	P-value*
Age in years, mean (SD)	64 (10)	63 (12)	0.26
Male gender, n (%)	128 (58%)	344 (48%)	0.011
Lung Function			
FVC %, mean (SD)	71 (19)	65 (19)	<0.001
DLCO %, mean (SD)	51 (21)	57 (23)	<0.001
Tobacco Smoker, n (%)	176 (80%)	363 (51%)	<0.001
Pack years, mean (SD)	36 (29)	18 (23)	<0.001
ILD subtype			
IPF, n (%)	93 (42%)	273 (38%)	0.30
CTD-ILD, n (%)	46 (21%)	191 (27%)	0.08
Fibrotic HP, n (%)	37 (17%)	117 (16%)	0.90
IAPAF, n (%)	2 (< 1%)	18 (3%)	0.15
Unclassifiable/Other ILD, n (%)	42 (19%)	112 (16%)	0.24

ILD = interstitial lung disease; FVC = forced vital capacity; DLCO = diffusing capacity of the lung for carbon monoxide; IPF = idiopathic pulmonary fibrosis; CTD-ILD = Connective tissue disease-ILD; HP = Fibrotic Hypersensitivity pneumonitis. Total sample size for subjects with available data on radiologic emphysema, N= 931. Categorical variables presented as n (%); continuous variables presented as mean (SD). Exception for participations: FVC, n= 913; DLCO, n= 843; tobacco smoker, n= 905; pack years, n= 665

Table E7. Causes of death and location at time of death among deceased subjects stratified by tobacco smoking status (n=533)

Characteristics of Deceased Subjects	Tobacco Smoker	Tobacco Non-Smoker	Total Cohort
<i>Tertiary center cohort</i>	<i>n=279</i>	<i>n=131</i>	<i>n=410</i>
Causes of death			
Pulmonary fibrosis/Acute exacerbation of ILD, n (%)	51 (18%)	25 (19%)	76 (19%)
Pneumonia/Sepsis, n (%)	9 (3%)	5 (4%)	14 (3%)
Ischemic heart disease/Heart failure, n (%)	11 (4%)	6 (5%)	17 (4%)
Malignancy, n (%)	3 (1%)	0 (0%)	3 (1%)
Undetermined, n (%)	79 (28%)	26 (20%)	105 (26%)
Other/unknown, n (%)	126 (45%)	69 (53%)	195 (48%)
Location at time of death			
Hospital, n (%)	51 (33%)	30 (48%)	81 (38%)
Hospice, n (%)	24 (16%)	3 (5%)	27 (13%)
Other health care facility, n (%)	1 (1%)	1 (2%)	2 (1%)
Home, n (%)	7 (5%)	2 (3%)	9 (4%)
Unknown, n (%)	70 (46%)	26 (42%)	96 (45%)
<i>Non-tertiary center replication cohort</i>	<i>n=59</i>	<i>n=64</i>	<i>n=123</i>
Causes of death			
Pulmonary fibrosis/Acute exacerbation of ILD, n (%)	23 (39%)	16 (25%)	39 (32%)
Pneumonia/Sepsis, n (%)	3 (5%)	6 (9%)	9 (7%)
Ischemic heart disease/Heart failure, n (%)	9 (15%)	11 (17%)	20 (16%)
Malignancy, n (%)	3 (5%)	3 (5%)	6 (5%)
Undetermined, n (%)	21 (36%)	28 (44%)	49 (40%)
Location at time of death			
Hospital, n (%)	40 (68%)	37 (58%)	77 (63%)
Hospice, n (%)	1 (2%)	2 (3%)	3 (2%)
Other health care facility, n (%)	2 (3%)	6 (9%)	8 (7%)
Home, n (%)	16 (27%)	19 (30%)	35 (28%)

**Undetermined cause of death annotated for subjects who died in-hospital with multifactorial or unclear cause of death at time of death certification. *Unknown cause of death for patients who died outside of hospital where cause of death and location were unknown.*

Table E8. Additional Models Assessing the Association between tobacco smoking and mortality in the tertiary center cohort (n=1163)

Model	HR	95%CI	P-value*
Unadjusted model	1.85	1.49 - 2.29	<0.0001
Adjusted model			
Model 1	1.77	1.43 - 2.20	<0.0001
Model 2	1.71	1.37 - 2.12	<0.0001
Model 3	1.72	1.39 - 2.14	<0.0001
Model 4	1.71	1.33 - 2.19	<0.0001
Model 5	1.65	1.28 - 2.12	<0.0001

Definition of abbreviations: CI = confidence interval; HR=hazard ratio; ILD=interstitial lung disease

*Computed using Cox proportional hazard models.

Model 1 assessing tobacco smoking with adjustment for age, sex, forced vital capacity at ILD diagnosis, diffusing capacity of the lungs for carbon monoxide at ILD diagnosis, ILD subtype, and antifibrotic therapy.

Model 2 = Model 1 with further adjustment for CT honeycombing.

Model 3 = Model 2 with further adjustment for presence of progressive pulmonary fibrosis.

Model 4 = Model 3 with further adjustment for radiologic emphysema.

Model 5 = Model 4 with further adjustment for hypothyroidism and coronary artery disease.